

COLLEGE OF ACCOUNTANCY AND BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

Students' Preference towards Online Conducive Learning Environment in the College of Accountancy and Business Administration at Northeastern College

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ABSTRACT

This research study aims to analyze students' perceptions of the extent to which an Online Conducive Learning Environment contributes to, and potentially enhances, their overall learning experience. A combination of quantitative and phenomenographic research design was utilized to collect data from fourth-year undergraduate BS Accountancy and BS Business Administration of Northeastern College. The Online Conducive Learning Environment was introduced as a primary educational tool intended to cover traditional face-to-face teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings of the study perceived that Online Conducive Learning Environment has a positive effect for the students in terms of time management and accessibility.

The insights gained from this study provide a deeper understanding of students' experiences with Online Conducive Learning Environment, revealing potential gaps between the intended use of such platforms and students' actual engagement with them. By offering a detailed examination of students' perceptions, this study serves as a critical resource for educators seeking to assess and refine both their face-to-face and online teaching strategies. This framework offers a valuable lens through which educators can reassess their use of technology and make more informed decisions about how to integrate Online Conducive Learning Environment more effectively into their instructional practices to enhance the overall student learning experience.

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DEDICATION

This research paper is dedicated to the **family** of the researcher who gives their unwavering support all throughout the research study. Their endless support and encouragement have been the driving force of this research. With sincere gratitude, this research is dedicated to **Dean Clemente P. Claro, Jr., CPA, Ph.D.**, whose invaluable guidance, mentorship, and academic expertise have significantly contributed to the successful completion of this research study. Dedicated to the **respondents** whose generous participations and honest responses have made this research possible. Their invaluable contributions have enriched the findings of this study. We look up and dedicate this whole study to our **Almighty God**, who gave the strength, knowledge, wisdom, protection, and will to continue this study.

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CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

The global outbreak of COVID-19, caused by the novel coronavirus, has profoundly disrupted various sectors, with education being one of the most affected. To mitigate the spread of the virus, countries worldwide imposed widespread closures of educational institutions, halting face-to-face teaching and affecting millions of students. Initially, in early February 2020, school closures were limited to China and a few other countries severely impacted by the virus. However, by mid-March 2020, the number of countries enforcing school closures had escalated to nearly 75. As of March 10, 2020, UNESCO reported that the closure of schools and universities had left approximately one in five students globally without access to education (UNESCO, 2020). By the end of April 2020, 186 countries had implemented nationwide school closures, affecting roughly 73.8% of the world's enrolled learners (UNESCO, 2020).

While these closures were necessary to contain the spread of COVID-19 through social distancing measures, they posed significant challenges for educational systems, disrupting academic schedules and putting a strain on conventional methods of learning. With educational institutions closed indefinitely, there was a pressing need for alternative solutions to ensure the continuity of education. In response, many educational institutions around the world pivoted to online learning platforms as a temporary measure to complete academic curricula. This transition, though initially disruptive, has led to innovations in education, particularly in the adoption of digital technologies that have traditionally been slow to gain traction in many educational systems.

The rapid shift to online learning, however, has revealed both opportunities and challenges. On the one hand, it has highlighted the potential for digital interventions to enhance access to education and provide flexible learning options, especially during times of crisis. On the other hand, the effectiveness of e-learning, particularly in developing countries, remains a subject of debate. The effectiveness of online education hinges on factors such as the availability of suitable devices, reliable internet connectivity, and institutional preparedness. As Muthuprasad (2021) notes, the lack of technical infrastructure in many developing countries exacerbates the challenges of adopting online learning, as limited access to devices and inadequate bandwidth significantly hinders the ability of students to fully engage with e-learning platforms.

Moreover, while the shift to digital education has offered an opportunity for educational innovation, it has also underscored the need for a rethinking of traditional pedagogical approaches. Educational systems globally have relied heavily on lecture-based teaching and in-person interactions, and this transition to online platforms has required rapid adaptations in both content delivery and assessment methods. According to Johnson et al. (2020), the move to digital learning necessitated the development of new teaching strategies, including asynchronous learning models, virtual classrooms, and the integration of multimedia resources to create more interactive and engaging learning experiences. Furthermore, the shift to e-learning has highlighted the need for continuous professional development for educators to effectively navigate these new technologies and pedagogical approaches (Bates, 2020).

Northeastern College is committed to providing quality education that is accessible not only to those with economic means but also to those who face financial challenges (Northeastern College's Philosophy, Section 1 of the Administrative Manual). The institution envisions itself as the Valley's true "mint of wisdom," with the goal of shaping students into exemplary leaders who influence and promote goodwill within their communities. This vision emphasizes the development of students who serve as positive role models and contribute meaningfully to society. In line with its core values to deliver quality education, Northeastern College continually evaluates and adapts its services to ensure they meet the evolving needs of students and the broader community. The institution is committed to remaining responsive to the changing demands of the educational landscape, embracing new technologies, and fostering a flexible learning environment. By integrating emerging technological advancements, Northeastern College seeks to enhance its educational offerings, ensuring that students are well-prepared for the challenges of an increasingly digital world. This proactive approach underscores the institution's dedication to delivering an education that is both relevant and accessible, preparing students for success in a rapidly changing global context.

This study aims to examine students' preferences regarding online conducive learning environment in relation to their personal time management and how these preferences impact their productivity and performance, considering their physical, mental, and emotional readiness. By comparing students' experiences with both face-to-face and online learning environments, the research will explore how different learning setups affect their ability to engage and perform. Specifically, it will investigate how the physical comfort, mental preparedness, and emotional well-being of students influence their effectiveness in each mode of learning. The findings will provide valuable insights into how educational institutions can optimize learning environments to enhance student productivity and well-being.

This study is designed to assess the preference of online schedule of the five districts in the College of Accountancy and Business Administration; Accountancy, Management Accounting, Marketing Management, Human Resource Development and Management, and Financial Management students of the first semester school year 2020- 2023. The data gathered will be used to assess the preferable set up of the students in terms of the discussed area.

A. Statement of the Problem

Generally, the purpose of the study aims to examine the students' preferences towards schedule conduciveness. Specifically, this study answers the following questions.

➤ *Demographic Profile of the Respondents in Terms of the Following:*

- Year level
- District

➤ *Is There Any Effect of Online Learning Environment to the Following Curriculum Activities:*

- Attendance in discussion
- Submission of requirements
- Quizzes and Examination

➤ *What are the Effects of Online Learning Environment to the Student's Preparedness and Efficiency in the Following Area:*

- Physical
- Mental
- Emotional

B. Significance of the Study

- To School – this study will be helpful to be aware on the positive impact of the online class schedule to students.
- To Faculty/Employees – Instructors can evaluate the effectiveness of the online classes they conducted.
- To legal community – this study will be helpful to them in widening their perspectives when it comes to the outcome of the online classes.
- The future researchers – they can use the study for their future studies on the similar topic.

C. Scope and Delimitation

This study will focus on the preferences and favorable factors on students in terms of their productivity in balance with their personal life. The factor of students' time management is the primary consideration. The result will just be limited to *fourth year students at the College of Accountancy and Business Administration*.

D. Definition of Terms

- Accountancy is the practice of recording, classifying, and reporting on business transactions for a business.
- Business Administration is the administration of a commercial enterprise. It includes all aspects of overseeing and supervising the business operations of an organization.
- COVID-19 is a contagious disease caused by the coronavirus SARS-CoV-2.

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Recent research on online learning readiness emphasizes the importance of technological self-efficacy, student motivation, and self-regulation in determining whether learners are prepared for online education. Ally (2019) identifies that readiness is multifaceted, involving not only technical skills but also psychological factors such as learners' motivation and attitudes toward online learning. According to Bawa (2016), online learning readiness has a strong predictive relationship with student success, highlighting the critical role of self-efficacy and the ability to adapt to online learning environments. Lee, Choi, and Lee (2017) explored students' readiness for online learning through the lens of cognitive and emotional factors, arguing that effective learning strategies and emotional regulation are essential for students to thrive in online courses. Moreover, recent research by Carter et al. (2018) found that students' self-efficacy beliefs in using technology for educational purposes significantly impact their engagement and persistence in online courses. In terms of technological readiness, studies have shown that students with higher computer literacy are more likely to succeed in online learning environments (Shen & Wang, 2019). This is consistent with Bates (2019), who emphasized the role of technology infrastructure and students' comfort with digital platforms in shaping their readiness for online learning.

Furthermore, the need for effective technical support in fostering students' readiness for online education has been underscored by Chen et al. (2017). Self-Regulated Learning in Online Education Self-regulated learning (SRL) is increasingly recognized as a cornerstone for success in online education, as learners must navigate the challenges of time management, goal setting, and independent learning (Panadero, 2017). According to Broadbent and Poon (2015), students who can self-regulate their learning, such as by setting goals and managing their time effectively, are more likely to succeed in online courses. This aligns with Zimmerman's (2017) model of SRL, which emphasizes planning, self-monitoring, and self-reflection as essential processes for students to manage their learning effectively. Research by Artino and Stephens (2016) found that self-regulation directly influences online learners' motivation and achievement. These findings were supported by Roca and Gagné (2018), who argue that SRL is even more critical in online education, where the lack of face-to-face interaction can make it harder for students to stay motivated and organized. Additionally, Kizilcec et al. (2017) found that students' metacognitive skills, which are central to SRL, are predictive of both their persistence in online courses and their overall academic performance. Technological tools designed to support SRL, such as online progress tracking and reminders, have been shown to enhance students' ability to regulate their learning effectively. Zhao et al.

(2018) found that incorporating adaptive learning technologies into online courses helps students track their progress and adjust their strategies, improving self-regulation and learning outcomes. Time Management and Academic Performance Time management remains one of the most critical factors in online learning success, particularly given the flexible nature of online courses. Studies show that effective time management is directly linked to better academic performance and reduced stress (Misra & McKean, 2019). Hodges et al. (2018) suggest that students who manage their time well in online courses are better able to meet deadlines and maintain a balanced academic workload. Recent studies by Li and Wang (2019) demonstrate that students with strong time management skills tend to perform better academically in online settings, as they are more likely to organize their learning activities and avoid procrastination. Conversely, Gupta and Kumar (2019) found that poor time management leads to procrastination, lower academic achievement, and greater feelings of stress in online learning environments. The role of digital tools in time management has also gained attention. Brusilovsky et al. (2019) found that time management applications integrated into online learning platforms helped students stay organized, set priorities, and allocate study time more effectively. This is in line with findings by Kumar and Soni (2018), who concluded that students using digital planners and time-tracking apps demonstrated better time management and higher academic performance in online courses. Interplay Between Readiness, Self-Regulation, and Time Management The interaction between readiness for online learning, self-regulation, and time management is complex and intertwined. Recent research suggests that students who exhibit readiness for online learning, combined with high self-regulation and effective time management, are more likely to succeed academically in online settings (Palloff & Pratt, 2019). According to Wang and Zhang (2019), these three factors—readiness, self-regulation, and time management—work together to influence online students' ability to complete tasks on time, stay motivated, and achieve their learning objectives. Rocca and Gagné (2018) argue that online course designers can foster these qualities by incorporating structured elements like progress trackers, interactive content, and regular feedback, which help students manage their learning more effectively. Furthermore, Yuan and Kim (2019) found that students who received personalized time management tips and self-regulation strategies from their instructors had significantly higher completion rates in online courses. Future research should continue to explore how these factors interact and identify strategies to support students in developing the necessary skills for success in online learning environments.

Table 1: Conceptual Framework

INPUT	PROCESS	OUTPUT
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The demographic profile of the respondents as to educational attainment and occupation. • The effects of online schedule to the productivity of students in terms of exam, quizzes, attendance, and activities. • The physical, mental, and emotional preparedness of the students. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research on Theory background and related studies. • Limiting the variables. • Data gathering using the assigned research instrument. • Data analysis on: age, gender, civil status, educational attainment and occupation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The main preference of students towards online class schedule.

Research indicates that there are many effects of online schedule to the students. As an input, the gathered information will be the process through survey questionnaire in the means of Google form.

Fig 1: Paradigm of the Study

CHAPTER THREE METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

It discusses how the researcher gathered the information and data needed in the procedures of data collection and instrument use. It also discussed the types and methods of research, and the research locale where the study was conducted.

B. Population

The population will be focused on the College of Accountancy and Business Administration. The college has five (5) respective districts; Accountancy, Management Accounting, Marketing management, Financial Management and Human Resource Development Management. Per district, Fifty percent of the total number of fourth year students will be the respondents.

C. Sampling Technique

The researcher uses purposive sampling, also known as judgmental, selective, or subjective sampling, is a form of non-probability sampling in which researchers rely on their own judgment when choosing members of the population to participate in their surveys.

This survey sampling method requires researchers to have prior knowledge about the purpose of their studies so that they can properly choose and approach eligible participants for surveys conducted using online survey platform; Google Form

D. Statistical Treatment

➤ *The Statistical Instruments to be used for the Analysis of Data to be Gathered as Follows:*

- Simple frequency counts and percent were used as statistical treatment to determine the personal profile of the respondents. Frequency distribution was used for the profile of the respondents with the formula of:

$$P = \frac{f \times 100}{N}$$

Where:

P= Percentage

f= Number of respondents

N= Total population 100=Construct

- Weighted mean was used to determine the levels of conduciveness to the effect to the student. Frequency distribution, weighted mean and rank were determining the effect of incarceration of their parents to their children.

$$x = \frac{\sum \sum^n / i (x * w)}{\sum \sum^n = 1 w_i \quad i}$$

Where:

W= weighted average

n= number of terms to be average

w_i= weights applied to x values

XX_i= data values to be average

E. Documentary Analysis

The researchers gathered necessary information from Northeastern College. The gathered data were students' perception about their experiences on the conduciveness of online schedules in terms of Quizzes, Attendance, and Lectures.

F. Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers gathered the data by the use of Google forms. A questionnaire was designed in order to gather insights and comments about online classes. The questions were divided in 3 categories; Physically, Mentally, and Emotionally this is to analyze major fields to see the effect whether beneficial or inconvenient in connection to their productivity and performance in quiz and examination and attendance. This is designed to gather responses about their insights on their readiness and overall experience towards online classes.

G. Data Analysis and Presentation

Descriptive statistics methods of analysis were used to analyse the data collected from the students who experience both face-to-face classes and online classes. A scale of 1 - Strongly Agree, 2-Agree, 3- Neutral, 4- Disagree, and 5- Strongly Disagree was designed to gather respondents' personal experiences in connection to their preference in online.

H. Research Instrument

The questions were formulated by the researchers in accordance with its relevance to the objective of the interview. The researchers based the questions on the information needed to satisfy the research questions. The questionnaire checklist was used to gather respondents' insight towards their preference of the online schedule. To arrive an in-depth information from the respondents the researcher conducted interviews which might not be included or reflected in the survey questionnaires. Although interview where quite informal, the researcher was able to collect ample data that gave greater clarity on the responses of the respondents.

Questionnaire is a set of questions arrange in sequence and designed to be self-administrated. The instrument was used on the presumption that the respondents where literate and clearly motivated and willing to participate. The principal tool which was used in data gathering was a structural questionnaire that contains six major parts

Table 2: The Weighted Mean and Distribution of Rank used to Determine Likert Scale where one Being the Highest and Five Being the Lowest

Scales	Qualitative Description	Rank
0.00-1.00	Strongly Agree	1
1.01-2.0	Agree	2
2.01-3.00	Neutral	3
3.01-4.00	Disagree	4
4.01-5.00	Strongly Disagree	5

CHAPTER FOUR

PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

A. Student's Preferences Towards Online Quiz and Examinations

Table 3: Online Quiz/Exam Provides Me More Time to Focus on Answering Without Any Pressure from My Instructor Because of the Setup.

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	35	22.4
AGREE	56	35.9
NEUTRAL	58	37.2
DISAGREE	3	1.9
STRONGLY DISAGREE	4	2.6

As presented above, 35 (22.4%) respondents answered strongly agree, 56 (35.9%) respondents agree, 58 (37.2%) respondents are neutral, 3 (1.9%) respondents disagree, and 4 (2.6%) respondents strongly disagree. It showed that most of the respondents are neutral.

Table 4: Online quizzes/exams lessen pressures in terms of Submission/Deadline

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	22	14.1
AGREE	80	51.3
NEUTRAL	39	25
DISAGREE	13	8.3
STRONGLY DISAGREE	2	1.3

As presented above, 22 (14.1%) respondents strongly agree, 80 (51.3%) respondents agree, 39 (25.00%) respondents are neutral, 13 (8.3%) respondents disagree and 2 (1.3%) respondents strongly disagree. It showed that most of the respondents agreed.

Table 5: Online quiz/exam helps me to be more organized in prioritizing which subject to take first.

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	25	16
AGREE	68	43.6
NEUTRAL	48	30.8
DISAGREE	11	7
STRONGLY DISAGREE	4	2.6

As presented above, 25(16%) respondents strongly agree, 68(43.6%) respondents agree, 48(30.8%) respondents are neutral, 11 (7%) respondents disagree, and 4 (2.6%) respondents strongly disagree. It showed that most of the respondents agree.

Table 6: Online Quiz/Exam Provides me the Opportunity to Digest the Questions Properly because I am in the Comfort of my House

RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	29	18.7
AGREE	74	47.4
NEUTRAL	40	25.6
DISAGREE	10	6.4
STRONGLY DISAGREE	3	1.9

As presented above, 29(18.7%) respondents strongly agree, 74(47.4%) respondents agree, 40(25.6%) respondents are neutral, 10(6.4%) respondents disagree, and 3(1.9%) respondents strongly disagree. It showed that most of the respondents agree.

Table 7: Online Quiz/Exam Makes Me Time Conscious and Organized in Submitting My Exams on Time

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	30	19.2
AGREE	61	39.1
NEUTRAL	46	29.5
DISAGREE	10	6.4
STRONGLY DISAGREE	9	5.8

As presented above, 30(19.2%) respondents strongly agree, 61(39.1%) respondents agree, 46(29.5%) respondents are neutral, 10(6.4%) respondents disagree, and 9(5.8%) respondents strongly disagree. It showed that most of the respondents agreed.

B. Student's Preferences towards Online Attendance

Table 8: I Can Attend Class Without Being Late Because of Traveling To School

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY	49	31.4
AGREE		
AGREE	71	45.5
NEUTRAL	28	18
DISAGREE	6	3.9
STRONGLY DISAGREE	2	1.2

As presented above, 49 (31.4%) respondents strongly agree, 71(45.5%) respondents agree, 28 (18%) respondents are neutral, 6 (3.9%) respondents disagree, and 2 (1.2%) respondents strongly disagree. It showed that most of the respondents agreed.

Table 9: Absenteeism We're Minimized because Even If I'm Sick, I Can Still Attend My Class

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	59	37.8
AGREE	69	44.2
NEUTRAL	17	11
DISAGREE	8	5.1
STRONGLY DISAGREE	3	1.9

As presented above, 59 (37.8%) respondents strongly agree, 69(44.2%) respondents agree, 17 (11%) respondents are neutral, 8 (5.1%) respondents disagree, and 3 (1.9%) respondents strongly disagree. It showed that most of the respondents agreed.

C. Student's Preferences towards Online Activity

Table 10: Organizing and Time Management are well Observed because I Can Prioritize which Subject Activity Needs to do First

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	27	17.3
AGREE	82	52.6
NEUTRAL	40	25.6
DISAGREE	5	3.2
STRONGLY DISAGREE	2	1.3

As presented above, 27(17.3%) respondents strongly agree, 82(52.6%) respondents agree, 40(25.6%) respondents are neutral, 5(3.2%) respondents disagree, and 2 (1.3%) respondents strongly disagree. It showed that most of the respondents agreed.

Table 11: I Can Express Freely my Creativity in my Activities without being Ashamed to be Judged by my Classmates

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	27	17.3
AGREE	87	55.8
NEUTRAL	34	21.8
DISAGREE	8	5.1
STRONGLY DISAGREE	0	0

As presented above, 27(17.3%) respondents strongly agree, 87(55.8%) respondents agree, 34 (21.8%) respondents are neutral, and 8 (5.1%) respondents disagree. It showed that most of the respondents agreed.

Table 12: It is Easier to do the Activity because of the Availability of Resources

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	26	16.7
AGREE	91	58.3
NEUTRAL	31	19.9
DISAGREE	7	4.5
STRONGLY DISAGREE	1	0.6

As presented above, 26 (16.7%) respondents strongly agree, 91(58.3%) respondents agree, 31 (19.9%) respondents are neutral, 7 (4.5%) respondents disagree, and 1 (0.6%) respondent strongly disagrees. It showed that most of the respondents agreed.

Table 13: It is Easier to Submit the Activity on the Online Platform.

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	18	11.5
AGREE	78	50
NEUTRAL	48	30.8
DISAGREE	10	6.4
STRONGLY DISAGREE	2	1.3

As presented above, 18(11.5%) respondents strongly agree, 78(50%) respondents agree, 48(30.8%) respondents are neutral, 10(6.4%) respondents disagree, and 2(1.3%) respondents strongly disagree. It showed that most of the respondents agreed.

Table 14: Even if I am not Feeling Well, I can do and Submit my Activity on Time Without Sacrificing my Health

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	42	26.9
AGREE	76	48.8
NEUTRAL	25	16
DISAGREE	10	6.4
STRONGLY DISAGREE	3	1.9

As presented above, 42(26.9%) respondents strongly agree, 76(48.8%) respondents agree, 25 (16%) respondents are neutral, 10(6.4%) respondents disagree, and 3(1.9%) respondents strongly disagree. It showed that most of the respondents agreed.

D. Physically Preparedness of Students towards Online Class

Table 15: I am More Active in Terms of Participating in Online Classes

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	20	12.8
AGREE	56	35.9
NEUTRAL	66	42.3
DISAGREE	12	7.7
STRONGLY DISAGREE	2	1.3

As presented above, 20(12.8%) respondents strongly agree, 56(35.9%) respondents agree, 66(42.3%) respondents are neutral, 12(7.7%) respondents disagree, and 2 (1.3%) respondents strongly disagree. It showed that most of the respondents were neutral.

Table 16: I am Eager to Finish Every Task I Need to do Without being Dependent on my Classmate

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
STRONGLY AGREE	24	15.4
AGREE	82	52.6
NEUTRAL	42	26.9
DISAGREE	7	4.5
STRONGLY DISAGREE	1	0.6

As presented above, 24(15.4%) respondents strongly agree, 82(52.6%) respondents agree, 42(26.9%) respondents are neutral, 7(4.5%) respondents disagree, and 1 (0.6%) respondent strongly disagrees. It showed that most of the respondents agreed.

Table 17: I am Eager to Finish Every Task I Need to do Without being Dependent to my Classmate

RESPONSES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	24	15.4
Agree	82	52.5
Neutral	42	26.9
Disagree	7	4.5
Strongly disagree	1	0.64

As data presented. 24 (15.4%) respondents answered strongly agree, 82 (52.5%) are agree, 42 (26.9%) respondents are in neutral, while 7 (4.5%) respondents are disagreeing, and 1 (0.64%) respondent chose strongly to disagree. It shows that most respondents are agree.

Table 18: I can Balance my Time in School and doing my Errands at Home

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	34	21.8
Agree	73	46.8
Neutral	39	25
Disagree	10	6.4
Strongly disagree	0	0

As presented above, 34(21.8%) respondents strongly agree, 73 (46.8%) respondents agree, 39(25%) respondents are neutral, and 10(6.4%) respondents disagree. Therefore, most respondents agreed.

Table 19: Even there are a Lot of Tasks to do in School, I Feel Less Tired During Online Class

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	15	9.6
Agree	79	50.6
Neutral	41	26.3
Disagree	12	7.7
Strongly disagree	9	5.7

As shown,15 (9.6%) respondents answered strongly agree, 79 (50.6%) are agree, 41 (26.3%) respondents are in neutral, while 12 (7.7%) respondents are disagreeing, and 9 (5.7%) respondents chose strongly to disagree. It showed that most respondents are agree.

Table 20: In Terms of Family Gathering, I don't have Any Worries in Failing to do my Responsibilities in School

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	29	18.4
Agree	74	47.4
Neutral	44	28.2
Disagree	5	3.2
Strongly disagree	4	2.5

As presented above, 29 (18.4%) respondents answered strongly agree, 74 (47.4%) are agree, 44 (28.2%) respondents are neutral, while 5 (3.2%) respondents are disagreeing, and 4 (2.5%) respondents strongly disagree. It showed that most respondents agreed.

E. Mentally Preparedness of Students towards Online Class

Table 21: I am more Creative in doing my Task and in Participating my Online Class

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	14	8.9
Agree	75	48
Neutral	60	38.4
Disagree	7	4.5
Strongly disagree	0	0

As data presented, there are 14 (8.9%) respondents who strongly agree, 75 (48%) respondents agree, 60 (38.4 %) respondents are neutral, and 7 (4.5%) respondents disagree It shows that most respondents agree.

Table 22: I don't Get Information Overload Even it was Given at the Same Time

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	9	5.7
Agree	67	42.9
Neutral	66	42.3
Disagree	11	7
Strongly disagree	3	1.9

As shown, 9 (5.7%) respondents strongly agree, 67 (42.9%) respondents agree, 66 (42.3%) respondents are neutral while 11 (7%) respondents disagree, and 3 (1.9%) respondents strongly disagree. Therefore, the data shows that most respondents agree.

Table 23: I am not Pressured in Performing my Task and in Participating

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	12	7.7
Agree	75	48
Neutral	59	37.8
Disagree	10	6.4
Strongly disagree	0	0

As presented above, 12 (7.7%) respondents answered strongly agree, 75 (48%) respondents agree, 59 (37.8%) respondents are neutral while 10 (6.4%) respondents are disagreed. The data shows that the majority agreed.

Table 24: I am Confident in Submitting my Tasks

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	23	14.7
Agree	82	52.5
Neutral	44	28.2
Disagree	7	4.5
Strongly disagree	0	0

As shown, 23(14.7%) respondents answered strongly agree, 82(52.5%) respondents agree, 44(28.2%) respondents are neutral, and 7(4.5%) respondents are disagreed. Therefore, it shows that most respondents are agree.

Table 25: I am not Worrying if I have other Things to do with the Same Schedule to my Online Class Because I have my Phone for me to Attend my Class Anywhere

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	30	19.8
Agree	69	44.2
Neutral	40	25.6
Disagree	13	8.3
Strongly disagree	4	8.9

As data presented, 30 (19.8%) respondents answered strongly agree, 69 (44.2%) respondents agree, 40 (25.6%) respondents are neutral, 13 (8.3%) respondents are disagreeing, and 4 (8.9%) respondents strongly disagreed. It shows that most respondents agreed.

F. Emotional Preparedness of Students Towards Online Class

Table 26: I Feel Safer in the Comfort of my House while Attending my Classes Virtually

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	40	25.6
Agree	76	48.7
Neutral	35	22.4
Disagree	4	2.5
Strongly disagree	1	0.6

As presented above, there are 40 (25.6%) respondents who strongly agree, 76 (48.7%) respondents agree, 35 (22.4%) respondents are neutral, 4 (2.5%) respondents disagree, and 1 (0.6%) respondent answered strongly disagreed. Data shows that most respondents agreed.

Table 27: I am More Assured in my Performance in Online Class

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	16	10.2
Agree	63	40.4
Neutral	68	43.6
Disagree	6	3.8
Strongly disagree	3	1.9

As shown above, 16 (10.2%) respondents answered strongly agree, 63 (40.4%) are agree, 68 (43.6%) respondents are neutral, while 6 (3.8%) respondents are disagreeing, and 3 (1.9%) respondents strongly disagree. Data shows that majority of respondents are neutral.

Table 28: I Have More Time to Myself and to my Family without Sacrificing my Responsibilities as a Student Because of Online Class

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	32	20.5
Agree	72	46.1
Neutral	44	28.2
Disagree	7	4.5
Strongly disagree	1	0.6

As data presented, 32 (20.5%) respondents are strongly agreed, 72 (46.1%) respondents are agreed, 44 (28.2%) respondents are neutral, 7 (4.5%) respondents are disagreeing, and 1 (0.6%) respondent strongly disagree. It shows that the majority agreed.

Table 29: I Feel More Relax in the Comfort of my House During Online Classes

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	28	17.9
Agree	76	48.7
Neutral	45	28.8
Disagree	5	3.2
Strongly disagree	2	1.3

As presented above, 28(17.9%) respondents answered strongly agree, 76(48.7%) respondents say they agree, 45 (28.8%) respondents are neutral, 5(3.2%) respondents are disagreeing, and 2(1.3%) respondents strongly disagreed. Therefore, data shows that most respondents agreed.

Table 30: I am not Overthinking Unnecessary Things Like Failure to Submit my Activities, Quizzes, and Examinations on Time Because I Can Easily Track my Progress Virtually

RESPONSE (S)	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE (%)
Strongly agree	22	14.1
Agree	63	40.4
Neutral	47	30.1
Disagree	16	10.2
Strongly disagree	8	5.1

As shown, 22 (14.1%) respondents strongly agree, 63 (40.4%) respondents agree, 47 (30.1%) respondents are neutral, 16 (10.2%) respondents disagree, and 8 (5.1%) respondents are strongly disagreed. So that, it shows that most respondents are agree.

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

➤ *Based on the Findings on this Study, the Following are the Conclusions:*

- In terms of student's preferences in taking online quizzes and examinations, Majority of the respondents agreed on the convenience if having it virtually. No time pressure, time management, and being organized were observed as the consensus benefit of the students in this area.
- In terms of student's preferences with their attendance during online classes, Majority of the respondents agreed on the advantage of having online attendance to lessen absenteeism and tardiness.
- In terms of student's preferences in taking their activities online, Majority of the respondents agreed that it is easier for them to do their online tasks organized, creative, because of the availability of the resources online.
- In connection to their physically preparedness, Majority of the respondents agreed on the usefulness of online classes wherein they can be more active in participating in their discussions and submitting their activities confidently.
- In connection to their mentally preparedness, Majority of the respondents agreed that it is easier for them to do their task virtually without being pressured and having information overload.
- In connection to their emotionally preparedness, Majority of the respondents agreed that online classes were helpful for their time management, balancing family and self-time responsibility and attending classes virtually lessen their negative overthinking towards their performance.

➤ *Based on the Findings on this Study, the Following are the Recommendation:*

- Online classes can boost students' confidence in doing their responsibility as student, encouraging them to apply it in face-to-face classes will be a good progress with their performances.
- Considerations in students' welfare in connection to their physical, mental, and emotional prepared should also be observe for them to be motivated in their overall performance.
- Activities, quizzes, and examinations shouldn't pressure students instead it should be their motivation to strive and to study well.
- Students' interest should be considered for them to be more active and by doing this, subject objectives, learning and assessment materials can be prepared well to cater the needs of the students and to achieve the desires learning outcomes.

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APPENDIX

➤ *Questionnaire*

Name (Optional):_

Year:

District:

Direction: By using the scale of 1 - Strongly Agree, 2-Agree, 3- Neutral, 4- Disagree, and 5- Strongly Disagree. Rate your personal experiences in connection to your preference in online schedule you had. All information you shared will be just used for research purposes and it will be strictly confidential.

In connection to your productivity and performance in Quiz and Examination

Questions	1	2	3	4	5
1. Online quiz/exam provides me more time to focus in answering without any pressure from my instructor because of the set up.					
2. Online quiz/exam lessen pressures in terms of submission/deadline.					
3. Online quiz/exam helps me to be more organized in prioritizing which subject to take first.					
4. Online quiz/exam provides me opportunity to digest the questions properly because I am in the comfort of my house					
5. Online quiz/exam makes me time conscious and organized in submitting my exams on time.					

In connection to your Productivity and Performance in Attendance

Questions	1	2	3	4	5
1. I can attend the class without being late because of travelling to school.					
2. Absenteeism was minimized because even I'm sick, I can still attend my class.					

In connection to your productivity and performance in Activity

Questions	1	2	3	4	5
1. Organizing and time management is well observed because I can prioritize which subject activity needs to do first.					
2. I can express freely my creativity in my activities without being ashamed to be judged by my classmates.					
3. It is easier to do the activity because of the availability of resources					
4. It is easier to submit the activity in online platform					
5. Even I am not feeling well, I can do and submit my activity on time without sacrificing my health.					

Physically Preparedness in having exam, quizzes, activity, and in attending my online class

Questions	1	2	3	4	5
1. I am more active in terms of participating in online classes.					
2. I am eager to finish every task I need to do without being dependent to my classmate					
3. I can balance my time in school and doing my errands at home					
4. Even there are a lot of tasks to do in school, I feel less tired during online class.					
5. In terms of family gathering, I don't have any worries in failing to do my responsibilities in school.					

Mental Preparedness in having exam, quizzes, activity, and in attending my online class

Questions	1	2	3	4	5
1. I am more creative in doing my task and in participating my online class.					
2. I don't get information overload even it was given at the same time.					
3. I am not pressured in performing my task and in participating.					
4. I am confident in submitting my tasks					
5. I am not worrying if I have other things to do with the same schedule to my online class because I have my phone for me to attend my class anywhere.					

Emotional Preparedness in having exam, quizzes, activity, and in attending my online class

Questions	1	2	3	4	5
1. I feel safer in the comfort of my house while attending my classes virtually					
2. I am more assured in my performance in online class.					
3. I have more time to myself and to my family without sacrificing my responsibilities as a student because of online class.					
4. I feel more relax in the comfort of my house during online classes.					
5. I am not overthinking unnecessary things like failure to submit my activities, quizzes, and examinations on time because I can easily track my progress virtually.					